

A Uniaxial *Hysteretic Superelastic* Constitutive Model Applied to Additive Manufactured Lattices

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ABSTRACT

Lattice materials with superelastic properties offer great potential for engineering applications, as they are able to undergo large deformations while ensuring the reversibility of the deformations due to stress-induced phase transformation. Adequate prediction of the mechanical response of lattice materials requires models that properly capture the deformation mechanisms of the internal architecture and the material response of the parent material. To analyze large-scale lattices by means of the finite element method, numerical efficiency becomes crucial. For this purpose, we propose a simple approach relying on beam-based modeling in combination with a uniaxial superelastic constitutive material model. The latter is based on polynomial functions, which make it easy to take customer-based material data into account being especially important for additive manufactured materials. To verify our constitutive model, a comparison with a well-established standard model is performed. The capabilities of the beam-based model to predict the mechanical response of lattice materials are evaluated by the comparison to high-fidelity models using continuum elements. We show that beam-based modeling is able to capture the governing deformation mechanisms of the investigated lattices and that our constitutive model is able to capture the smooth stress–strain response of the experimental data that are not available to the standard model.

1 | Introduction

Lattice materials offer great potential in engineering applications as their internal architecture governs their effective mechanical response. With progressing additive manufacturing techniques, lattice materials with custom-tailored mechanical properties are easily manufactured. In combination with superelastic parent materials, such as NiTi alloys, lattice materials allow for large deformation states while retaining reversibility of the deformations due to stress-induced phase-transformation.

An adequate prediction of the mechanical response of lattice materials requires models to properly capture both the deformation mechanisms of the lattice microstructure and the material

response of the parent material. The modeling of lattice materials by means of the finite element method (FEM) is typically more efficient when beam elements are used instead of continuum elements. For beam elements, uniaxial constitutive material laws can be considered sufficient to model the superelastic response of the parent material.

In the literature, various models can be found for describing the superelastic behavior of the parent material at the macroscale, such as plasticity-based models and models derived through thermodynamic potentials, see [3] for an overview. However, these models require considerable effort to implement in the FEM framework of interest and to individually calibrate them to the available experimental data. Especially for additive manufactured

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FIGURE 1 | The experimental data are indicated by the black dots. Curve fit for loading and unloading for the UHYPEL model and piecewise linear curve describing the starts and ends of the phase transformation considered for the ABAQUS superelasticity model.

materials, where various production parameters influence the resulting material properties, for example, [6], we see a need for a simpler approach that is easily available to engineers.

In this work, the uniaxial superelastic hysteretic stress–strain response is modeled by piecewise polynomial functions. Case distinctions allow to follow proper loading and unloading responses, respectively. The implementation is realized within the framework of a hypoelastic constitutive law. Numerical simulations by means of the FEM are performed to verify the implementation by comparison with standard models based on [1, 2] available in ABAQUS. Additionally, various lattice materials are studied to show the model’s capabilities of being suitable for real applications. All simulations are performed with ABAQUS 2023/Standard (*Dassault Systèmes Simulia Corp., Providence, RI, USA*).

2 | FEM Implementation of Constitutive Law

A uniaxial hysteretic superelastic material model based on the hypoelastic UHYPEL interface of ABAQUS is implemented to account for the material behavior in a beam element. For this element, the interface requires the tangential Young’s, or elastic modulus, $E_T = d\sigma/d\varepsilon$, and the Poisson ratio, $\nu(\varepsilon)$, to be defined depending on the strain state.

Considering the experimental data given in Figure 1, we assume that the stress–strain relation is sufficiently described by third-order polynomials during the phase transformation process of loading (austenite to martensite) as well as the retransformation process of unloading (martensite to austenite) and by a linear polynomial for the fully transformed material (martensite phase). We also consider linear polynomials for unloading prior to full transformation and reloading prior to full retransformation since corresponding experimental data are not available. This is schematically given in Figure 2 for a general loading sequence. The stress as a third-order polynomial reads as follows:

$$\sigma(\varepsilon) = a\varepsilon^3 + b\varepsilon^2 + c\varepsilon, \quad (1)$$

FIGURE 2 | Uniaxial stress–strain curve of a general loading sequence, where the solid line represents the loading curve, the dotted line is the martensite phase, the dashed line represents the unloading curve, and the dash–dotted lines represent reloading/unloading prior to full re-transformation/transformation. The numbers 1–11 attached to the arrows indicate the loading sequence.

as a function of strain, ε , where a, b , and c are coefficients obtained by curve fitting of the experimental data set. The coefficients are $a = b = 0$ for the linear polynomials. Considering conservative systems, the tangential elastic modulus is obtained via the following:

$$E_T(\varepsilon) = \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial \varepsilon} = 3a\varepsilon^2 + 2b\varepsilon + c. \quad (2)$$

The elastic moduli corresponding to the considered stress–strain relations are denoted by $E_{iL,T}$ for loading, $E_{iU,T}$ for unloading, E_M for the pure martensite phase, and $E_{iT,T}$ for unloading prior to full transformation as well as reloading prior to full retransformation. We assume that the phase transformation starts immediately, that is, the stresses at the start of the transformation and at the end of the retransformation are zero, $\sigma_{iL}^S = \sigma_{iU}^E = 0$. Here, the superscripts S and E denote start and end of the transformations, respectively, the subscripts L and U denote loading and unloading, respectively. Furthermore, tension and compression is indicated by an additional subscript t and c, respectively. Since we only have experimental data from compression tests, we assume that there is no difference between compression and tension. We further assume that the stress at the end of the transformation is the same as the stress at the start of the retransformation, that is, $\sigma_{iL}^E = \sigma_{iU}^S$. The same is assumed to hold true for the corresponding strains $\varepsilon_{iL}^S = \varepsilon_{iU}^E = 0$ and $\varepsilon_{iL}^E = \varepsilon_{iU}^S$, respectively. To distinguish between loading and unloading, we introduce an incremental strain value, $\Delta\varepsilon$, as a user-defined field variable via the USDFLD interface. To facilitate correct predictions of unloading and reloading loops at intermediate transformation strains, we utilize case distinction. Therefore, we additionally introduce user-defined field variables, for example, to distinguish between loading and reloading. For the sake of brevity, the procedure is not explicitly outlined. However, it is implicitly shown in Figure 2. Note that the user-defined field variables are evaluated before the UHYPEL routine is called, hence, they are one increment behind. This can be considered negligible as long as the time discretization of the solution procedure is fine enough. The Poisson ratio is assumed to be constant, that is, $\nu(\varepsilon) = \nu = 0.3$.

FIGURE 3 | Base cells of *stiff* (left) and *compliant* lattice (right) as well as corresponding 8x8 lattices.

TABLE 1 | Geometrical dimensions of the analyzed lattices, where L_i denotes the length in i -direction, t is the thickness of the struts, and h is the out-of-plane thickness, compare Figure 3. The surface A is used for evaluating stresses.

$N \times N$	$L_i = L$ in mm	t in mm	$A = Lh$ in mm ²
1 × 1	10	0.5	10
8 × 8	80	0.5	80

3 | Methodology

3.1 | Modeling Setup

We study two different types of 2D lattices, namely, a diamond lattice being further referred to as *stiff* and a cambered diamond lattice showing a rotated center by 45° being further referred to as *compliant*, compare Figure 3. To demonstrate differences between material and structural response, we use two different configurations of each lattice type, namely, an infinite lattice, that is, a single base cell with periodic boundary conditions (PBCs) applied, and a finite lattice comprised of 8 × 8 base cells. The dimensions of the lattices are summarized in Table 1.

For predicting the mechanical response of the infinite lattices, we set up three different models, namely, a high-fidelity model using continuum elements, further referred to as continuum model, and two beam models. The continuum model is meshed by plane stress elements with quadratic shape functions in conjunction with the ABAQUS superelasticity model (ASM) based on [1, 2]. The beam models are set up using linear Timoshenko beam elements with 25 section points in conjunction with either the ASM or the UHYPEL. The effective Poisson's ratio of the beam section due to axial strain is not taken into account, as we have found that this can lead to convergence difficulties regarding the lattice simulations. Note that the beam models do not take into account aggregated material at joints, for example, [5]. For the UHYPEL model, we have to directly define the transverse shear stiffness of the beams. For this purpose, we define the transverse shear in the material section of the input file via *TRANSVERSE SHEAR from which ABAQUS can determine the corresponding stiffness according to the Austenite phase, G_A , based on $E_A = 100$ GPa and $\nu = 0.3$, compare Table 4 in Section 3.2. The continuum model using the ASM will be referred to as cASM, the corresponding beam model as bASM, and the beam model in conjunction with the UHYPEL as bUHYP. The meshes of the

TABLE 2 | Coefficients for the tangential elastic moduli resulting from the curve fit and used for the UHYPEL model.

	a	b	c
$E_{tL,T}$	2.5791426E+7	-1.790820E+6	4.5940E+4
E_M, E_{tT}			6.7159E+4
$E_{tU,T}$	2.3729021E+7	-1.082987E+6	1.7937E+4

beam models are created by using the Python libraries `gustaf` and `splinepy`. To obtain a geometry for the infinite lattices that is suitable for meshing with continuum elements, we extract the splines describing the geometry and further process them to obtain a surface-based geometry. The PBCs are set up with the help of `medtool`. For the finite lattices, we only compare the bASM and bUHYP models as we expect excessive computation costs for the cASM.

3.2 | Material Parameter Calibration

In uniaxial compression experiments of additive manufactured NiTi samples, we can observe transformation-induced plasticity during cyclic loading. After a certain number of loading cycles, we find a stabilized cycle that we use to calibrate our models. The data of the stabilized cycle are given in Figure 1.

To calibrate the bUHYP model, we perform curve fitting based on third-order polynomials for the transformation and retransformation processes using the Python package `scipy.optimize.curve_fit`. For the martensite phase, we consider a linear relation between stress and strain, once the maximum measured stress is reached. The corresponding polynomials are shown in Figure 1 with their resulting coefficients a, b , and c of Equations (1) and (2) summarized in Table 2.

To determine the input parameters for the ASM, we manually select stress–strain pairs corresponding to the start and the end of the transformation from austenite to martensite as well as vice versa, see Figure 1. Note that not all pairs can be chosen independently, as we consider linear stress–strain relations in the pure austenite and martensite phase. This is indicated by the piecewise linear curves connecting these pairs shown in Figure 1. The pairs are summarized in Table 3. Some algebraic manipulations yield the input parameters for the ASM given in Table 4.

TABLE 3 | Stress–strain pairs with respect to the experimental data with stresses in megapascal.

ε_{tL}^S	σ_{tL}^S	ε_{tL}^E	σ_{tL}^E	ε_{tU}^S	σ_{tU}^S	ε_{tU}^E	σ_{tU}^E
2.51E-3	2.51E+2	4.22E-2	5.74E+2	3.71E-2	2.13E+2	3.5E-4	3.57E+1

TABLE 4 | Input parameters for ASM. Elastic moduli and stresses in megapascal.

E_A	ν_A	E_M	ν_M	ε_L	σ_{tL}^S	σ_{tL}^E	σ_{tU}^S	σ_{tU}^E	σ_{cL}^S
1E+5	3E-1	7E+4	3E-1	3.4E-2	2.51E+2	5.74E+2	2.14E+2	3.6E+1	σ_{tL}^S

FIGURE 4 | Pure bending (left) and shear force bending (right) of a cantilever for beam and continuum models.

3.3 | Comparison Study

To verify that beam modeling is able to properly capture the mechanical response, a cantilever is subjected to a pure bending and a shear force bending load case (LC), for which we compare continuum with beam models using the ASM, see Figure 4 (left) and (right), respectively. We further verify our UHYPER model by comparing it with the ASM models and show the influence of the better fit to the experimental data. For the pure bending LC, the left end is clamped without constraining the transverse deformations and a rotation of $UR_3 = -0.6$ is prescribed at the right end. For the shear force bending LC, the left end is clamped without constraining the transverse deformations and a displacement of $U_2 = -3$ is applied on the right side. For the continuum model, a multiple point constraint is defined at the right side to allow the corresponding nodes to move only along a straight line defined by the reference node and one of the corresponding corner nodes, that is, a MPC using the slider option is used. The dimensions of the cantilever are $L_1 = 10$, $t = 1$, and $h = 1$ for the out-of-plane thickness.

To evaluate the predictive capabilities of the beam models, we carry out simulations based on the infinite lattices, where we aim at a comparison with the continuum model. For this purpose, we use two different LCs, namely, a compression and a pure shear LC. Both LCs are schematically depicted in Figure 5(i) and (ii), respectively. For the compression LC, a displacement is prescribed at node NW of $U_2 = -L/10$. For the pure shear LC, displacements of $U_1 = L/10$ and $U_2 = L/10$ are applied on nodes NW and SE, respectively. For the *stiff* lattice in combination with this LC, the strut connecting the corner nodes NW and SE is expected to buckle. To access the nontrivial solution path of the expected bifurcation problem, we apply a small initial moment at the center of the base cell. This kind of imperfection mimics the first eigenmode that would be obtained by linear eigenvalue analysis. For the sake of brevity, we only consider beam models for the nonlinear solution paths. It is worth noting that we do not consider any long wave instabilities arising from using more than one base cell, for example, [7].

Furthermore, we use finite lattices to investigate the influence of the boundary conditions (BCs) arising from a structural LC more common in engineering applications. For this purpose, the lattices are fully clamped at the left end and a displacement of $U_2 = L/10$ is prescribed at a reference node at the very right being tied to the nodes of the lattice at the right. This is schematically shown in Figure 5 (iii). Only beam models are used for the sake of numerical efficiency.

Note that we consider geometrically nonlinear behavior to account for large deformations. This causes ABAQUS to use logarithmic strain measures, which affects our UHYPER model. However, as long as the strains at the material level are small, this can be considered negligible, which is the case in our simulations. All simulations are conducted using the Newton–Raphson solution procedure.

4 | Results

ABAQUS inputs and results used to generate the figures within this section can be found in [8].

4.1 | Verification

In the following, for the cantilever model, the beam-based models are compared with the continuum model through moment–rotation curves for the pure bending LC and force–displacement curves for shear force bending LC, compare Figure 6 (left) and (right), respectively. The cASM and bASM models are in very good agreement for both LCs, indicating that the beam-based modeling approach can properly capture the deformation states. Note that we only consider slender geometries where the transverse shear deformation is not pronounced. The bUHYP model is more compliant at lower loads than the other models. This is based on the flatter slope in the lower loading range of the parent material, compare Figure 1. Furthermore, the unloading path prior to full transformation is different for the ASM and

FIGURE 5 | Compression (i) and pure shear (ii) LCs with PBC as well as structural LC (iii).

FIGURE 6 | Nodal moment–rotation curve of pure bending LC (left) and force–displacement curve of shear force bending LC (right) evaluated at the very right, where details are given on the right-hand side, respectively. Dotted lines represent curves obtained for higher loadings.

FIGURE 7 | Equivalent transformation strains of cASM (top) and bASM (bottom), where the first ($UR_3 = 0.24$) and second column ($UR_3 = 0.6$) correspond to pure bending LC and third ($U_2 = 1.2$) and fourth column ($U_2 = 3$) correspond to shear force bending LC. For the cASM, the default average threshold of 75% is used for averaging element output at nodes. For the bASM, the section point data are directly plotted without averaging. Note the different geometrical scaling in X_1 and X_2 directions.

the UHYPEL models. The bUHYP shows a different due to the case distinction implemented. For higher loads, the UHYPEL and ASM models show the same behavior. This is represented by the dotted lines. Contour plots of the equivalent transformation strains on the undeformed geometry are given for the cASM and bASM models in Figure 7. The difference of the two LCs lies in the evolution of the transformation zone. For the pure bending LC, this zone develops from both the top and the bottom fibers towards the neutral axis and is evenly distributed over the entire length of the beam. In contrast, for the shear force bending LC, the zone develops from the fixation on the left to the load application on the right. Within the evolving zone, the top and bottom fibers are fully transformed. A qualitative comparison between the continuum and beam models shows that the beam-based model is able to correctly capture the evolution of the zones.

4.2 | Infinite Lattices

To show that our beam-based model approach is suitable for describing the deformations of the lattices, stress–strain curves

of the models for the compression and pure shear LC are given in Figure 8 (left) and (right), respectively. The stresses are evaluated by using the corresponding reaction force at the master node NW (or SE) acting on the initial area A , which is given in Table 1. The normal strains are determined via $\epsilon_{22} = U_2^{NW}/L_2$. The shear angles are determined via, $\gamma_{12} = \arctan(U_1^{NW}/L_2) + \arctan(U_2^{SE}/L_1)$ leading for the considered case of pure shear to $\gamma_{12} = 2 \arctan(U_1^{NW}/L_1)$.

Note that we do not consider the changes in lengths, that is, we use engineering stresses and strains. For the compression LC, the models are in good agreement for both *stiff* and *compliant* lattices. As expected, the bUHYP shows a more compliant behavior in the lower loading range. For the pure shear LC, the *stiff* lattice shows a bifurcation for all three models based on the buckling of the strut connecting NW and SE. The bifurcation points are indicated by the dots. The shear stress–strain curve clearly indicates that the solution of the nontrivial path is more compliant and shows a similar shape to that of the *compliant* lattice. Contour plots of the equivalent transformation strains of the cASM are given for the compression LC in Figure 9. Note that for the

FIGURE 8 | Normal stress–strain curves of the compression LC (left) and shear stress–strain curves of the pure shear LC (right) for *stiff* (first and third column) and *compliant* (second and fourth column) type of lattice. For the pure shear LC of the *stiff* lattice, the dots indicate the bifurcation points, the thin dotted lines are associated with the corresponding trivial solution paths.

FIGURE 9 | Equivalent transformation strains of cASM for the compression LC with *stiff* (left) and *compliant* (right) lattices, where the first and third contour correspond to $\epsilon_{22} \approx -0.26$ and the second and fourth contour correspond to $\epsilon_{22} = -0.4$.

FIGURE 10 | Force–displacement curves of the finite lattices at the load application point (left) and contours of equivalent transformation strains at maximum loading (right) for *stiff* and *compliant* lattices using bASM. The beam elements are rendered by a factor of 2 and show values corresponding to the lowermost section points.

compliant lattice, the four-fold rotation symmetry is broken under loading.

4.3 | Finite Lattices

Force–displacement curves of the finite lattices are given in Figure 10 (left). The structural LC shows that the bUHYP is significantly more compliant than the bASM over a large loading range for both types of lattices since many regions are in a partly or low phase transformation state. This indicates that the ASM significantly overestimates the reaction forces during loading for the calibrated material. This is crucial for any application when operating in this strain range. Note that for the bUHYP model, a static stabilization is necessary to obtain a converged solution, especially during unloading. However, the artificial energy introduced is negligible compared to the strain energy.

Furthermore, contour plots of the equivalent transformation strain at maximum loading for both types of lattices using bASM are given in Figure 10 (right). The *stiff* lattice shows triangular regions that spread from center to the left and right edges. These regions are completely unaffected due to the stress shielding effects from the BCs. In contrast, the deformation is localized in triangular areas that spread from the center to the upper and lower edges. This results in some kind of pivotal point at the center. This is less pronounced for the *compliant* lattice.

5 | Summary

A uniaxial hysteretic superelastic material model for beam elements based on the hypoelastic UHYPEL interface of ABAQUS is presented, which can be easily tailored to custom-based experimental data. Numerical simulations by means of the FEM are performed to study the model’s capabilities to capture the

mechanical response of lattice materials. We use continuum and beam models with standard superelasticity models for the evaluation of the presented model.

Based on infinite lattice simulations, we show that the beam-based models agree very well with the predicted mechanical response of the high-fidelity models using continuum elements. The much higher numerical efficiency of the beam models allows us to further study large-scale lattice materials. We found that the standard model clearly deviates from our model in the lower loading regime. This can be attributed to the fact that our model considers more information from the original experimental data of the parent material. This leads us to the conclusion that the mechanical response predicted by our model can be considered more realistic than the standard model. In combination with much higher numerical efficiency, we provide a tool suitable for large-scale lattice simulations including nonuniform loading scenarios.

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